

ACCIDENT RECORDER AND SOS INFORMATION TECHNOLOGY

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ABSTRACT- Many times an accident goes unnoticed for hours before help comes. Due to all these factors, there is a high rate of mortality of accident victims. In addition to this, there is a delay in the ambulance reaching the hospital to the traffic congestion between the accident location and the hospital which increases the chances of the death of the victim. Although automobiles save us lots of traveling time, the risk increases in traveling because of the accidents. For the prevention of such accidents, we can use modern additional technologies. In the context of our project, we have used some sensors, electronic modules and a microcontroller unit which helps us in providing prevention from accidents, detects the accident if it occurs even after the preventive measures, and reports the ambulance service which consist of an eye blink sensor, temperature sensor, alcohol sensor, accelerometer, GPS module, motor, buzzer, led, etc., and all these devices are interfaced with the central microcontroller unit.

Keywords: *Sensor, Arduino Mega, AT mega, GPS, GPRS, GSM, Black box, SOS, MEMS.*

I. INTRODUCTION

In today's world, there is a severe increase in the use of vehicles. Such heavy automobile usage has increased traffic and thus resulted in a rise in road accidents. This takes a toll on the property as well as causes human life loss because of the unavailability of immediate preventive and safety facilities [1]. This embedded system can prevent the accident to occur and proper preventive measures are taken in this system. The ambulance service and the police station can easily find the location as the location along with the Google map link was sent to their smart devices with mobile network accessibility [2]. The system consists of an eye blink sensor, temperature sensor, alcohol sensor, accelerometer, GSM module, motor, buzzer, led, etc., and all these devices are interfaced with the central microcontroller unit.

As we are going to use an eye blink sensor for detecting sleep by setting a certain time limit, if the driver gets sleepy, we can warn him. Temperature sensor helps us in detecting the heat of the engine and if the engine is overheated then that of a normal condition, we can warn the driver. Alcohol sensor helps us in detecting if the driver is drunk or not. If he/she is over drunk the vehicle provides a warning and the engine stops functioning. Accelerometer detects the occurrence of the accident and sends a signal to the microcontroller for further functioning [3].

If an accident occurs, the location of the accident that we get from the GPS is sent to the ambulance service and police with the help of the GSM module. Everything might be all right after a simple accident so the driver can re-inform the ambulance service and police station in this case[5].

In this paper a black box for safety and investigation purpose is used. This black box record the audio, speed of the car, locations, which part of the car damaged, at what force the car get accident the vehicle monitoring technology has the potential to provide a wide range of safety benefits, including relatively inexpensive and continuous measurement of driving behavior and vehicle use, which is otherwise difficult to observe. A detailed report will be given to the user containing the recorded data in the memory, wired black box using MEMS accelerometer and GPS tracking system is developed for monitoring the accidents.

II. EXISTING SYSTEM

The Existing IOT SOS Service is an innovative idea which, when implemented to its full potential can be very vital to our society and can be very beneficial to a wide range of audiences. Our implementation included a prototype with an interface that showed its working and the extent to which it can be implemented. The description of all modules is provided which, when integrated provides a wide variety of functional requirements which include getting the location of the car and informing respective authorities of a crash. Also, the interface is represented through a website user-friendlily and provides the user with only the necessary and useful data that is required. As seen through our graph snapshot, we are able to receive data from our accelerometer 3-axis sensor through the GSM module via our cloud server and have displayed it in the form of a chart to indicate the car acceleration over a period of time [1] as shown figure 2.1.

Figure2.1 Block Diagram of proposed System

III. DESIGN OF THE SYSTEM

In this paper, there are four sensors used that are temperature sensor LM35, vibration sensor, gas sensor MQ3, and accelerometer ADXL345 are the primary inputs. LCD display, GPS6MV2, and GSMSIM900a are the primary outputs. The detail Hardware specifications are given in Table 3.1

Table 3.1 Hardware specifications

Arduino Mega	ATmega2560
GPS Module	NEO-6M (4800bps to 230400bps)
GSM module	Dual-Band 900/1800MHz
Temperature sensor	LM35 (-55°C to 150°C)
Alcohol sensor	MQ-4(0.04mg/L to 4 mg/L)
Vibration sensor	SW-420
IR sensor	Range 2-10 cm
LCD Display	JHD162A
Motor drive	L293D
DC motor	1500 RPM
Power supply	5V
Buzzer	95db
SD card module	3.3~5v

IV.HARDWARE ARCHITECTURE

The hardware setup consisted of the following sections as follows:

(a)Arduino: The board microcontroller on it which is ATmega328 is used as the main controller to manage the circuit accordingly”. “It is a well-known open-source microcontroller-based kit for creating digital devices and interactive tool that can interact with LED’s, LCD display, switches, GSM, flame sensor, Buzzer and many more”.

(b) Alcohol sensor MQ-4: Detects the presence of alcohol gas at concentrations from 0.04 mg/L to 4 mg/L, provides an analog resistive output based on alcohol concentration”

(c)Temperature sensor LM35:To operate over a -55°C to150°C temperature range, output voltage linearly- proportional to the Centigrade temperature”

(d) Accelerometer ADXL345: A small, thin, ultra-low power,3-axis accelerometer with high resolution (13-bit), that measures the static acceleration of gravity in tilt–sensing applications.

(e) A vibration sensor: To measures the amount and frequency of vibration in a given system, machine, or piece of equipment.

(f) GPS Module NEO-6MV2 : Used for navigation. The module simply checks its location on Earth and provides output data which is the longitude and latitude of its position. It is from a family of stand-alone GPS receivers featuring the high-performance box 6 positioning engine.

V. ATMEGA2560 MICROCONTROLLER

As Arduino Mega is based on ATmega2560 Microcontroller, the technical specifications of the Arduino Mega are mostly related to the ATmega2560 MCU. But nonetheless, let me give you a brief

overview of some important technical specifications of the Arduino Mega 2560 the detail specifications are given in Table 5.1

Table 5.1: Specifications of Arduino mega

Components	Range /Specifications
MCU	ATmega2560
Architecture	AVR
Operating Voltage	5V
Input Voltage	6V – 20V (limit)7V – 12V (recommended)
Clock Speed	16 MHz
Flash Memory	256 KB (8 KB of this used by boot loader)
SRAM	8 KB
EEPROM	4 KB
Digital IO Pins	54 (of which 15 can produce PWM)
Analog Input Pins	16

VI. NEO-6M GPS MODULE

The GPS gives us the next Arduino paper the ability to sense locations with the NEO-6M GPS module that can track 22 satellites and identify locations anywhere in the world. It can serve as a great launch pad for anyone looking to get into the world of GPS. They are low-power (suitable for battery-operated devices), affordable, easy to interface, and extremely popular with hobbyists. At the heart of the module is a GPS chip from U-blox – NEO-6M. The chip measures less than a postage stamp but packs a surprising number of features into its tiny frame. It can track up to 22 satellites over 50 channels and achieve the industry’s highest level of tracking sensitivity i.e., -161 dB, while consuming only 45 mA current. Unlike other GPS modules, it can perform 5 location updates in a second with 2.5m horizontal position accuracy.

VII. WORKING PRINCIPLE

In this system at first, we worked on the prevention of vehicle accidents and even after all the preventive measures applied if an accident occurs the system detects it. After the detection of a vehicle accident, the system automatically reports to the ambulance service and police station without any time loss so that the casualty might not lose his/her life due to late rescue.

The system is installed in the vehicle. As preventive measures for vehicle accidents, the sensors like MQ-4 alcohol sensors, IR sensors, and Vibration sensors are used. For the detection of vehicle accident accelerometer is installed and for reporting GPS module and GSM module are used. The motor (control switch) is used for engine control and the buzzer, led lights, etc. are used for warning during prevention. All these devices are interfaced with the central microcontroller (Arduino Uno) and (Arduino Mega) unit. Alcohol sensor helps us in detecting if the driver is drunk or not. If he/she is over drunk the vehicle provides a warning and the engine stops functioning. A vibration sensor is used for detecting the accident. Here we are using an IR sensor as a Temperature sensor that helps us in detecting the temperature of the engine and if the engine is overheated then in normal conditions, the driver is warned with a red colored LED. Accelerometer detects the occurrence of the accident and sends a signal to the microcontroller for further functioning. GPS module provides the location, speed, time, and date of a certain place where the vehicle is in real-time which provide SOS information as shown in figure 7.1.

Fig7.1: SOS Information

If an accident occurs, the accelerometer detects it and the location of the accident is obtained using GPS, and finally sends the information to the ambulance service and police with the help of a GSM module. The message obtained on a mobile phone consists of the location of the accidental place in the

form of a Google map link which will help the emergency units like ambulance service and police station to reach the casualty in time and rescue the lives. The vehicle unit consists of an alcohol sensor, vibration sensor, and temperature sensor as preventive measures for an accident, a buzzer, and red-light LEDs for alerts. First alcohol sensor detects the concentration of alcohol in the driver, if it is found below the threshold the motor rotates and the vehicle is ready to be driven.

Whenever alcohol is detected the motor stops. Similarly, the system will also check the temperature of the engine continuously and keeps alerting if found above the threshold value of engine temperature. The vehicle unit also consists of an accelerometer that keeps on informing the coordinate of vehicle position to the microcontroller. If it is found random, the GPS location tracker tracks and informs the emergency number with values of latitude, longitude, and Google map position using the GSM SIM module.

VIII RESULTS

The Accident Recorder and SOS Information system is based on Arduino Mega and Arduino UNO which gives accurate location details during an accident and it has the ability record vital information. The system uses a negative display for user interface. The overall kit is enclosed in a wooden box resembling a black box which shown in figure 8.1.

Fig 8.1: The overall kit is enclosed in a wooden box resembling a black box

The figure 8.2 shows a normal case in which the speed is under the safe limit at 162 RPM and shows an accident scenario. After the crash, if the temperature reaches a critical level, the system gives a warning alarm. It also has a gas sensor to detect the amount of alcohol consumed by the driver as shown in figure 8.3.

Fig 8.2 Normal bus

Fig 8.3 drunken drive alert

After the occurrence of an accident the vibration, IR sensor, and MEMS accelerometer gets activated and Arduino UNO gives information regarding the collapse to the figure8.4 GPRS module which detects the device's current location and sends messages via. SMS about the crash with a link consisting of the location

Fig 8.4 Message with live location

IX. CONCLUSION

Both SOS systems and black box technology contribute to improving road safety. SOS systems provide immediate assistance in emergencies, potentially reducing response times and increasing the chances of survival. Black boxes offer valuable data for analyzing accidents and identifying areas for improvement in vehicle design, driver behavior, and road infrastructure. It is important to note that the availability and functionality of SOS systems and black box technology may vary depending on the make and model of the vehicle. Additionally, the usage and privacy considerations surrounding black box data are subject to legal regulations and policies that vary across different jurisdictions. Overall, SOS systems and black box technology serve as important tools in promoting safety, enhancing emergency response capabilities, and providing valuable data for accident analysis and improvement in the automotive industry.

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